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**DESIGNING MULTI SENSORY ACTIVITIES FOR TEACHING PREPOSITIONS TO
THE YOUNG LEARNERS OF THE INTEGRATED JUBILATION MONTESSORI
CENTER OF BIÑAN (IJMC-B)**

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29 October 2024

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Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete
October 29, 2024

Acceptance Page

This special/capstone project prepared by **Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete** with the title: **“Designing Multi Sensory Activities for Teaching Prepositions to the Young Learners of the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B)”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Education Studies.

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Biographical Sketch

Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete was born in Makati City but grew up and currently lives in Biñan City, Laguna. She is a graduating 4th year college student taking up the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU), a public research university that has a virtual campus for open learning and distance education and a physical headquarters located in Los Baños, Laguna. Prior to enrolling at UPOU, she graduated Senior High School at St. Scholastica's College – Westgrove, which is located in Ayala Westgrove Heights, Silang, Cavite. She is an aspiring educator and is interested in pursuing a career in the field of education, particularly early childhood education and special education for children. She is dedicated to promoting quality education for young children and making a positive impact in their lives.

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Abstract

The special project that was developed is an instructional design for students in the Kindergarten level of the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B) to learn about the topic of prepositions under the subject of Language. The ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation) instructional design model was the methodological approach utilized in the instructional design project. Based on the assessment through a sit-in observation in the Kindergarten classroom and a discussion with the key personnel, the instructional needs identified is the integration of different sensory modalities in the learning activities through media, visuals and colorful instructional materials for motivation as the students were recognized as visual, auditory and kinaesthetic learners. On the other hand, the learning needs identified are the linguistic gap on the common mistakes with the use of prepositions in sentences and phrases. Although the IJMC-B follows the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum by the Department of Education (DepEd) across all grade levels, the topic of prepositions was not found in the curriculum for the Kindergarten level. The instructional design project aimed to design an instructional plan that involves multisensory activities and instructional materials, including slide presentations, flashcards, printed objects and printed worksheets for teaching prepositions. The four-step method of instruction serves as the inspiration for the methodology used for the flow of the instructional plan. The design of the learning activities utilized several learning theories including the multisensory approach, Social Learning Theory, positive reinforcement in operant conditioning and Activity-Based Learning.

Keywords: instructional design, multisensory approach, ADDIE instructional design model, Kindergarten, instructional plan, instructional materials

I. BACKGROUND

The Special Project Site

For the **planning phase** of the special project, an educational institution was identified in a residential community within the City of Biñan, Laguna which is the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B) located at Phase 2 Evergreen County, Jubilation Subd., Biñan City, Laguna that offers education for Pre-Kindergarten to Grade 10 students. A letter was sent to the key personnel of IJMC-B that involves the school head, Ms. Ma. Rovil L. Caingat, and guidance officer/senior faculty member, Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon to coordinate with them for the special project (see Appendix A). After their approval of the provided printed letter and consent form (see Appendix B), an instructional design project for the Kindergarten level was opted to ensure that the project was a beneficial and mutual gain for both parties. The rationale for this being that the Kindergarten, Primmer and Nursery are taught by only one teacher who manages the students in their weekly classes across all subjects.

A needs assessment is defined by the Office of Migrant Education (2001) as a systematic set of procedures used to identify needs, analyze their nature and causes and establish priorities for future action. According to Neaum (2016), through observation and assessment, we can learn about children's knowledge and skills, and we can use this information to ensure that our interactions with them and the things we offer are aligned with their needs and abilities. Thus, for the **analysis phase**, an assessment was carried out to identify the potential learning/performance

needs or gaps, as well as to gather information about the behaviors and interactions of the Kindergarten students within their learning environment to identify the potential instructional needs or gaps through a discussion with the gatekeeper and the Kindergarten teacher/implementer, as well as a sit-in observation in the Kindergarten classroom (see Appendix D). This will not only be beneficial but also fully support the aims and overall mission of the instructional design project that will be developed.

The Learning Environment

A set of findings were found during the sit-in observation in the Kindergarten classroom, which was supplemented by the insights provided by the gatekeeper and Kindergarten teacher/implementer about the learning environment of the Kindergarten students. In a research by Paul et al. (2017), it was found that the social interaction of the students and their ability to learn is impacted by the physical conditions of a classroom or any learning environment. In terms of the physical condition of the classroom, it was observed that the walls were colorful with child-friendly paintings, such as a boy and a girl sitting on building blocks, and letter-sized counting numbers and letter posters and small banners that were adhered to them. The size of the classroom was sufficient to hold less than 20 students, which is enough to hold the number of Kindergarten students and Primmer students who are less in number than them. The Kindergarten students and Primmer students share a classroom wherein the latter uses the classroom during their morning or AM classes, while the Kindergarten students use it during their afternoon or PM classes. It was the season of summer during the time of sit-in observation, and there were some inconveniences to the students and teachers in the classroom

that were observed. Despite having air conditioning and an electric fan, the air circulation and ventilation were inadequate due to the excessive heat and the classroom facing the direct sunlight. Paul et al. (2017) found that the physical conditions of any learning environment should be taken proper care of by designers as they have a significant impact on how students behave and learn, particularly in terms of their mental health.

In terms of the available materials, the resources found in the classroom were minimal, including a blackboard, a small television for facilitating videos and presentations, black and white or dull printed worksheets that are only often used in quarterly examinations and limited visual aids, which are utilized to teach students and assess their learning. A laptop, projector and speakers are available in the administration office for use.

The Target Learners

The Kindergarten students are a total of 15, consisting of ten boys and five girls, with an age range of 5 to 6 years old and serve as the target audience of the instructional design project. The students are Filipino citizens from upper lower to lower middle class families. IJMC-B follows the [K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum](#) by the Department of Education (DepEd) across all grade levels, including the Kindergarten level. A set of findings were found from the discussion and sit-in observation in terms of the strength/s and needs of the Kindergarten students. It was found that the students (1) are able to follow directions and read basic words, phrases and sentences, but have a little difficulty in writing long words and

sentences; (2) display common grammar mistakes, including the incorrect use of prepositions; (3) bilingual and can speak the languages of English and Tagalog, but mainly communicate in English, except during the subject of Filipino wherein they are encouraged to respond in Tagalog; (4) are recognized as visual, auditory and kinaesthetic learners and (5) do not have learning disabilities or require special assistance.

Based on the findings, the potential instructional needs identified is the integration of media, visuals and colorful instructional materials for both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. On the other hand, the potential learning or performance needs identified are the linguistic gap in the common mistakes with the use of prepositions in sentences and/or phrases, as well as the integration of different sensory modalities in the learning activities. The results from the assessment and observations in the analysis phase serves as the basis of the instructional design project.

II. INTRODUCTION

The special project that was intended to be developed is an instructional design for students in the Kindergarten level of the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B) to learn about the topic of prepositions under the subject of Language. The methodological approach utilized in the instructional design project is the **ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation) instructional design model**. According to Bates (2015), the ADDIE model has been successful due to factors such as quality design, clear learning objectives, well-structured content, managed workloads for teachers and students, the integration of media, student activities, and assessment that is closely linked to the intended learning outcomes. Thus, the ADDIE model was followed to have a systematic and structured approach to design, develop and implement an instructional plan and instructional materials for teaching the topic of prepositions to the target learners.

Based on the findings in the assessment of the target learners that was carried out, it was found that the potential learning or performance needs identified are the linguistic gap on the common mistakes with the use of prepositions in sentences and/or phrases. Upon looking into the DepEd Kindergarten Curriculum Guide, the K To 12 Basic Education Program for the Alternative Learning System (ALS) Learning Strand 1: Communication Skills (English), the MATATAG Curriculum Guide for Kindergarten and the DepEd K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum Guide presented to the staff of IJMC-B, the topic of prepositions, in particular, was not

found in the curriculum for Kindergarten. According to Woa Wene & Dayu Putri (2018), students often make a wide range of grammatical errors when learning the English language, such as the improper usage of prepositions.

The instructional design project focuses on enabling the Kindergarten students to identify, recognize and apply the use/s and function/s of prepositions for their vocabulary and language development. As an overview, a preposition is defined by the Oxford English Dictionary as a word that governs and often comes before a noun or pronoun and expresses a relationship to another word or element in the sentence or phrase. It serves to demonstrate the relationship between two words in a sentence or phrase, it typically does this between a noun, verb or adjective and a noun (including proper noun), pronoun, or gerund (verb in noun form) (Emile Education, 2020). Some of the basic prepositions include in, on, next to, in front of, close to and beside (Lumiere Children's Therapy, 2018). As children start to learn the English language, it might take them time to become proficient in the ability to use the appropriate words in the right places. Thus, the learning of prepositions is an important aspect of language development for young children. Prepositions, which include words such as up, over and behind are essential in making requests, following instructions and locating objects (Nicholas et al., 2019). Moreover, numerous questions on speech and language evaluations, educational evaluations and developmental testing require children to have an understanding of the prepositions (Rakovic Speech and Language Chat, 2021).

As mentioned in the assessment of the learning environment, the potential instructional needs is the integration of different sensory modalities in the learning

activities through media, visuals and colorful instructional materials due to the Kindergarten students being recognized as visual, auditory and kinaesthetic learners. Since the learning activities and assessments facilitated by the teacher are often textbook-based, according to the needs assessment (see Appendix D), the students don't often have the opportunities to engage in interactive learning activities. According to Moustafa (1999), researchers have recognized methods to effectively teach diverse learners who struggle in settings that use traditional methods, including multisensory approaches and learning styles theory, which have proven to be effective.

The *multisensory approach* utilizes many parts of the human brain that provides students with multiple ways for making connections, comprehending more concepts and retaining information (Main, 2021). According to Mercer & Mercer (1993)(cited in Moustafa, 1999), the multisensory approach is also known as visual-auditory-kinesthetic-tactile or VAKT which implies that students learn best when information is presented in different modalities, including activities that enable students to see, hear and touch. Considering the visual, auditory and kinaesthetic learning styles of the Kindergarten students, a multisensory approach was applied in the designing and development of the learning sessions to facilitate active participation, comprehension and retention of the topic of prepositions.

The learning activities presented in the instructional plan is underpinned by several learning theories. Firstly, the *Social Learning Theory*, where learning can occur through observing the actions of others (Cherry, 2022), through encouraging the students to follow the implementer in recognizing the prepositions by asking

them to repeat the words or going back and forth in flipping the flashcards. Secondly, the utilization of *positive reinforcement in operant conditioning* under the behavioral theory, which is the process of adding a rewarding stimulus after a behavior that increase the probability that the behavior will occur again in the future (Cherry, 2021), where the students are given treats or compliments, such as by clapping or by saying 'Good job!' or 'Very good!', every time they use the correct preposition. Thirdly, the utilization of *Activity-Based Learning*, which is a teaching approach where the content or material is implemented through a variety of activities to make learning more exciting and engaging (Smile Foundation, 2022), through demonstrations using real objects. For instance, in the application part for Learning Session No. 1 (see Appendix E), a student is asked to bring an object out of his/her bag and place them accordingly in a position of in, on, under or over and create their own sentence.

III. MAIN NARRATIVE AND SYNTHESIS

For the **design and development phase**, the instructional design project intended to (1) produce an instructional plan that involves multisensory activities for teaching prepositions for the implementer/s of the learning session/s to follow (see Appendix E) and (2) develop instructional materials, including the creation of slide presentations, flashcards, printed objects and printed worksheets (see Appendix F), and the preparation of videos, real objects, toys and boxes, for facilitating the learning activities.

The findings from the planning and analysis phase were considered in the designing and development of the instructional plan and instructional materials to ensure that they are aligned with the learning styles of the Kindergarten students and the available materials. As an overview, the instructional plan includes the designing of two learning sessions: “Prepositions: In, On, Under, Over” and “Prepositions: Behind, In Front Of, Beside, Between” that involves multisensory activities for the implementer/s to follow.

The methodology utilized for the flow of the instructional plan is inspired by the four-step method of instruction. According to Simmons (2018), the four-step method of instructional delivery is an essential tool used to affect learning, with steps including preparation, presentation, application and evaluation, which is utilized to relate the material in the lesson plan with the learner. The methodology for each of

the learning sessions is divided into preparation (involves a presentation), application (involves a presentation), assessment and concluding.

The learning theories utilized in the designing of the instructional plan includes the multisensory approach, Social Learning Theory, positive reinforcement in operant conditioning and Activity-Based Learning. The instructional plan requires the creation of instructional materials to facilitate the learning sessions, such as slide presentations, flashcards, printed objects and printed worksheets. The rationale for utilizing these instructional materials is for them to serve as visual aids to cater to the learning styles of the students. Visual aids are effective tools that can be utilized in the classroom by teachers to improve student interest, comprehension, and retention of material and concepts (Suite VariQuest Visual and Kinesthetic Learning, 2021). Online platforms such as Canva and Google Docs were used throughout the process of creating the instructional plan and instructional materials, which are both made available for download and print for the staff of IJMC-B. These online platforms were utilized as it allows for ease of accessibility, in which people can access the soft copy of the instructional plan and instructional materials at their convenience, making it convenient for them to utilize it in their lessons related to the topic of prepositions.

Moreover, as part of the design and development phase, a licensed teacher/tutor, Ms. Thea L. Abad, who mainly teaches pre-elementary learners and facilitates play-based learning activities, was sought for feedback on the learning activities presented in the instructional plan for improvement. Before the implementation phase, the instructional plan and materials were presented to the gatekeeper and implementer for evaluation and validation (see Appendices I and J).

Feedbacks for improvement from these key personnel were used to make the necessary adjustments to the instructional plan.

First Learning Session

For the **implementation phase**, the first learning session with the topic of “Prepositions of Place: In, On, Under, Over” in the instructional plan was pilot-tested during the subject of Language with a duration of 45 minutes, starting at 12:30 PM to 1:15 PM.

Following the methodology for the Learning Session No. 1 of the instructional plan, the preparation part includes an introductory activity where the students are introduced to the topic of prepositions of place through a set of flashcards that demonstrates each preposition, which were passed on to them for a closer look; a presentation that plays videos on prepositions where the implementer explains the prepositions involved; a slide presentation that displays examples using sentences with the corresponding images to help students understand the concept better; and a hands-on activity wherein the students categorize objects as in, on, under or over using a box, real objects and toys. Second, the application part includes a hands-on activity where each student brings out an object they own and place it in, on, under or over their chairs and creates their own sentences, wherein they are given treats and/or compliments for using the correct prepositions; and a slide presentation activity that show sentences with corresponding images, where students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions and read the complete sentences. Third, the assessment part includes the distribution of colorful printed worksheets for

the students to complete, which involves activities that include matching the correct prepositions of sentences and phrases with the images. Lastly, the concluding part includes the acquisition of the completed worksheets; and a brief review of the prepositions that the students have learned to emphasize the understanding of students in the lesson.

Second Learning Session

The second learning session with the topic of “Prepositions: Behind, In Front Of, Beside, Between” in the instructional plan was pilot-tested during the subject of Language with a duration of 45 minutes, starting at 7:45 AM to 8:30 AM.

The methodology for the Learning Session No. 2 of the instructional plan was followed. Firstly, the preparation part includes an introductory activity where the students are reviewed on the prepositions they learned in the first learning session through a demonstration using flashcards; a slide presentation that is displayed on the projector that plays videos on prepositions where the implementer explains the videos they watched after; and a slide presentation that explains the concept of prepositions, sharing that a preposition is a bridge, as well as examples using sentences with corresponding images where students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions. Secondly, the application part includes a hands-on activity where the students must follow an order as instructed the implementer by placing the object in a position of behind, in front of, beside or between using the boxes and printed objects; and a presentation where students practice the use of prepositions by encouraging them to fill-in-the-blanks of the sentences with the correct

prepositions. Thirdly, the assessment part involves the distribution of the printed worksheets that the students have to complete where they must match the correct preposition of the sentence and phrase as shown on each image, as read and explained by the implementer. Finally, the concluding part involves the acquisition of the completed worksheets; a review of the correct answers to each item in the worksheet; and a summary on the prepositions covered.

For the **evaluation phase**, it can be concluded that the implementers were able to follow and execute the process or methodology instructed in the instructional plan. The pilot-testing of the learning sessions allowed for observation on how the students responded to the learning activities and instructional materials presented to them. The attainment of the competencies, key understandings and learning objectives provided in the instructional plan were observed and achieved by the students. The preparation part introduces the topic that the students will learn and instantly engages them through demonstrations, presentations and learning activities using the instructional materials. The application part enabled the students to apply their learning of the topic through a hands-on activity that challenges their understanding, creativity, retention, vocabulary and increases their participation. The assessment part provides the implementer an understanding of the effectiveness of the learning session and an observation on how the students fared. Based on the marked evaluation worksheets, the students have achieved an average of 91.7% full mark on the first learning session. The concluding part enabled the students to reflect and evaluate their performance by reviewing the prepositions and their functions with the implementer.

The instructional design project has been pilot-tested with the implementation of the learning sessions in the instructional plan. However, there were a few challenges observed during the implementation phase:

- *Technical issues*: During the implementation of the first learning session, a technical issue occurred in terms of projecting the slide presentation on the small television. This was quickly resolved by displaying it on a laptop instead.
- *Adjustments made by the implementers*: During the implementation of the first learning session, the implementer exceeded the allotted time frame due to the students' pace in answering the printed worksheets and the implementer making sure that most of the students engage and participate in the learning activities. Moreover, a few parts of the slide presentation were not implemented by the implementer during the implementation of the second learning session, such as in the application part where the students are able to practice the use of prepositions through a fill-in-the-blanks activity. This was rationalized by the time constraints and the pace at which the students were answering the worksheets, as mentioned by the implementer.
- *Time constraints on the schedule of implementation*: The implementation for the second learning session was held back due to the implementer's inability to accommodate and make time for the learning session due to a planned and overloaded schedule for the students (i.e. class suspension, exam week, practice week for school events and graduation). The followed plan of action is the implementation of the second learning session to the Grade 1 students in the upcoming school year, formerly Kindergarten students, to ensure that

the objectives of the instructional design project are aligned with the target learners.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the methodological approach of the ADDIE instructional design model, the instructional design project was able to accomplish the necessary steps with the fulfillment of the analysis phase through carrying out an assessment of the special project site, the learning environment and target learners to identify the learning/performance and instructional needs or gaps, which are the linguistic gap on the common mistakes with the use of prepositions and the needs for the integration of media, visuals and colorful instructional materials for increased engagement. This guides the design and development phase to ensure that the objectives of the project which is creating an instructional plan that involves multisensory activities for teaching prepositions and instructional materials, including slide presentations, flashcards, printed objects, printed worksheets, videos, real objects, toys and boxes, were appropriate and aligned to meet the needs and interests of the learning environment and target learners. The implementation phase of the learning sessions to the target learners has been crucial in the evaluation phase to determine the effectiveness and relevance of the instructional design project.

In terms of the response and behavior of the Kindergarten students to the learning sessions and instructional materials, the students have shown engagement and participation through showing interest in the learning activities presented, such as by being attentive and raising their hands eagerly to be called by the implementer/s (see Appendices G and H). These were promoted by the learning theories underpinned in the design of the instructional plan, including the

multisensory approach, Social Learning Theory, positive reinforcement in operant conditioning and Activity-Based Learning which were found to be effective and aligned with the learning styles of the target learners. Moreover, the students were able to practice and apply their knowledge of basic prepositions to enhance their vocabulary and language development.

Based on the observations and evaluations, it can be concluded that the students have attained the learning objectives stated for the learning sessions through the observations found during the implementation of the learning sessions, the evaluations made by the gatekeeper (see Appendices C, I and J) and the marked evaluation worksheets completed by the students. However, despite the objectives of the instructional design project and the learning objectives for the learning sessions being fulfilled, there were still challenges encountered.

A few recommendations can be made on the challenges observed during the implementation phase of the instructional design project:

- *On the challenge of technical issues:* The implementer must choose the technological device/s available in the school, such as a laptop, television and/or projector, that will be utilized to display the slide presentations before the implementation of the learning session/s and ensure that they are working. In case the technological devices are unavailable for use, the slide presentations can be downloaded, printed and turned into a flipbook. According to Sitzmann et al. (2010), interruptions are a regulation obstacle since they make it more difficult to focus on the content and achieve learning

objectives. When trainees are interrupted, there is a need to adjust their action plan to accommodate the interruption.

- *On the adjustments made by the implementers:* The pace of the implementer in teaching the learning sessions must be aligned with the pace at which the students respond with the learning activities and the estimated time of completing the worksheets for evaluation. According to Simmons (2020), effective pacing is related to student engagement as it affects the speed of moving through a learning session and the rate of delivery for different parts of the lesson. A pacing that is too slow can lead to disengagement among students. On the other hand, a pacing that is too fast might cause some students to not understand the lesson, get lost or become discouraged. For the future use of the instructional plan and materials, modifications can be made in the process of following the instructional plan by the implementer, such as by excluding some parts in the instructional plan or the slide presentations, to ensure that the learning sessions are aligned to the learners.

Along with the needs identified, the absence of the topic of prepositions in the curriculum guide for Kindergarten by DepEd K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and other curriculum guides, including the MATATAG Curriculum and the K To 12 Basic Education Program for the Alternative Learning System (ALS), asserts the need for its inclusion and introduction in the Kindergarten curriculum in the Philippines. Prepositions in the English language is a well-known challenge for learners of English as a second language, as they are one of the most difficult areas (Lindstromberg, 2010) (cited in Woa Wene & Dayu Putri, 2018). Moreover, this asserts the need to determine the most effective approaches for teaching the proper

use of prepositions through the help of teachers and instructional designers in the Philippines for the students to develop an increased understanding and acquisition of prepositions in the English language.

V. REFLECTION

Upon reflection, the objective of giving back to my community and conducting an instructional design project was, indeed, both beneficial and mutual gain for both parties. The conclusions and recommendations stated above must be taken into consideration for university students and instructional designers who are planning to undertake a similar instructional design or community-based projects in the future. The experiences, performances, challenges and lessons throughout the development of the instructional design project which were documented in this e-Portfolio can help guide future projects. Along with the challenges observed during the implementation phase, the feedback received from the implementers and the responses of the students were taken into consideration to improve the overall effectiveness of the instructional plan and instructional materials. Thus, a suggested revised version of the instructional plan that focuses on effective pacing to ensure that the pace of the implementer of the learning sessions align with the response of the students was also designed (see Appendix K).

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Letter of Request to the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Binan (IJMC-B)

Addressed to Ms. Ma. Rovil L. Caingat, School Head, and Ms. Marycon A.

Bataanon, Guidance Officer/Senior Faculty Member:

February 22, 2023

Ms. Ma. Rovil L. Caingat & Ms. Bataanon
School Head / School Staff
Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan
Ph2 Evergreen County, Jubilation Subdivision
Biñan City, Laguna 4024

Dear Ms. Caingat and Ms. Bataanon,

I hope this letter finds you well. My name is Reine Gerbie Labarrete, a 4th-Year college student at University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) under the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program.

As part of our program requirements in EDS 199 Special Project, I am tasked to develop an instructional design or a research project in an organization/institution that is involved in or organizes educational programs. I think that opting for conducting an instructional design (i.e. designing, developing and implementing instructional materials, resources, etc.) may be more beneficial for both parties. I am highly encouraged to coordinate with a representative in the organization/institution who will serve as an external adviser or gatekeeper in conducting and developing the project. The external adviser or gatekeeper shall be able to guide, monitor and evaluate my outputs and performance.

I am reaching out to inquire if it would be possible for me to coordinate and collaborate with the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B) for the project. I believe that by working with IJMC-B, I can contribute to its mission and vision while fulfilling the requirements of my program. Your guidance and support throughout the duration of the project would be invaluable to me. Enclosed with this letter is the special project consent form, which requires the approval and signature of the external adviser or gatekeeper.

Thank you for considering my request. I eagerly await your favorable response.

Sincerely yours,

Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

APPENDIX B

Approved Project Consent Form by the Student, Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete, and the Gatekeeper, Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon:

Special Project in Bachelor of Education Studies	
<p>The first page of the consent form is to be accomplished by the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University.</p> <p>For our students: Kindly complete this form in consultation with the head of the institution and/or the person-in-charge, department head or supervisor, the special project gatekeeper, depending on where you will conduct the project.</p>	
Student's name: <u>Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete</u>	
Student number: <u>2020-03031</u>	Batch of entry in UPOU: <u>1T AY 2020-2021</u>
Email address: <u>rllabarrete@up.edu.ph</u>	Contact number: <u>09178706268</u>
Academic Term: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 st term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 nd term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3 rd term AY: <u>2023-2024</u>	
Special Project Outcomes	
After completing the course, the student should be able to:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Apply knowledge of educational research analyzing and evaluating an educational issue or problem; OR apply knowledge of instructional design in developing and testing an instructional program, resource, or technology;2. Critically reflect on their experiences as they complete their special project; and3. Demonstrate ethical practice and desirable professional work attitudes and skills	
Special Project Requirements	
Project Preliminary Report	the implementation sessions of the practicum plan with at least one: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Instructional Design Project: implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199• Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199
Class/Learner/ Program/ Needs Analysis	an analysis/ report based on observation of actual practice, interview of teacher/ department head/ program head, and or other pre-assessment or evaluation tools
Project Plan	a plan highlighting the specific activities and strategies that the student will implement to accomplish the assigned project task or work based on educational theories, concepts, and principles
Project Work	the implementation sessions of the project plan with at least one: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Instructional Design Project implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199• Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/

external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199

- Project ePortfolio the collection of documents, reports, and relevant attachments showcasing learning from and analysis of the whole practicum experience, and providing evidence of achievement and accomplishments
- Project eJournal a brief reflective journal on the insights gained, problems experienced and solutions made, and areas for improvement
- Project presentation the presentation of the highlights of the special project which will be assessed by the FIC and monitored by the BES Program Chair

Student's signature: _____

Date: February 21, 2024

To the Head of Institution/ Practicum Supervisor,

I would like to express my deepest gratitude for extending your expertise and guidance to our student. With your help, our student will be able to achieve the objectives of the special project, gain invaluable knowledge and understanding of the work involved and required in the profession, as well as develops the skills needed in the field. Again, thank you very much.

Sincerely,

Asst. Prof. Leynard Gripal
Faculty-In-Charge, 2T 23-24 EDS 199 – Special Project

Gatekeeper/ External Adviser's Approval

Duties of the Gatekeeper:

- assigns tasks
- guides student in his/her accomplishment of tasks
- encourages creativity and innovation
- monitors progress
- provides regular feedback and comments
- signs practicum logs
- evaluates teaching demonstration/implementation or testing of output

This signifies my consent for the BES student to conduct special project in our institution/ organization/community class provided that s/he will abide by our policies and regulations. I understand that the student is expected to showcase creative and innovative application of theories and principles that s/he has learned from your undergraduate program in an actual professional work; thus, we shall provide the student with opportunities for such endeavor.

Name and Signature above Printed Name: ~~XXXXXXXX~~ MARYCON A. BATAANON

Designation: Guidance OFFICER and Senior Faculty Member

Name of institution/ organization: Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Binan Inc.

Office number: 044 549 6708 Email address: augustkesnelbataan@gmail.com

Date: March 1, 2024

APPENDIX C

Special Project Logs Signed and Evaluated by the Gatekeeper:

EDS 199
Special Project
Logs

This log is for the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University. The student should complete the log after each session, to be validated by the project gatekeeper/ external adviser, depending on the chosen project. The last column is for the project's gatekeeper on the student's work. When the project is finished, a scanned copy of this log sheet shall be submitted as part of the special project portfolio.

Student's name: Reine Gerbie Labarrete

Student number: 2020-03031 Batch of entry in UPOU: AY 2020-2021

Email address: rrlabarrete@up.edu.ph Contact number: 09178706268

Academic Term: 1st term 2nd term / 3rd term AY: 2023-2024

Project Locale: Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan

Student's Project Main Task: Designing Multi Sensory Activities for Teaching Prepositions to the Young Learners at the Integrated Jubilation Montessori Center of Biñan (IJMC-B)

Project Week	Specific Date	Specific Time	Duration	Validated by	Highlights	Insights	Gatekeeper's Feedback
	February 23, 2024	3:00 PM – 3:30 PM		 Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon	I visited IJMC-B and I handed out a printed letter addressed to the key personnel of IJMC-B, which are the school head, Ms. Ma. Rovil L. Caingat and guidance officer/senior faculty member, Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon that discusses my intentions on	Ms. Caingat expressed her approval and support and assigned Ms. Bataanon to be my external adviser/gatekeeper for the special project.	

					coordinating with them in developing my special project.		
	March 1, 2024			 Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon	The consent form was signed and approved by the external adviser/gatekeeper.		
	April 18, 2024	5:15 PM – 5:50 PM		 Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon	I was assigned to create an instructional plan and instructional materials for the Kindergarten learners enrolled in IJMC-B, particularly on the subject of Language.	Ms. Bataanon: I coordinated the topic to be discussed by Pre- Elem teacher and ask Reine to produce the materials needed to that suited topic.	Ms. Bataanon: I instructed Reine to use a realistic materials so that the learners will be motivated to participate in the discussion.
				Ms. Thea Ysabelle L. Abad	The instructional plan was presented to the content expert who is a teacher/tutor that mainly teaches pre-elementary learners and facilitates play-based learning to evaluate the content of the instructional plan.		Ms. Abad: The details of the Instructional Plan are well constructed, clear, and easy to follow. The activities are appropriate for the learners and are very engaging. It would be better if the video is explained after presenting. Overall, the plan is learner-centered, and was prepared and written well.

	April 26, 2024	2:00 PM – 3:00 PM		 Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon	The instructional plan and instructional materials needed to facilitate the learning session/s were presented to the gatekeeper and implementer.	Ms. Bataanon: The instructional plan and materials are very realistic and the learners will be motivated to participate in the discussion.	Ms. Bataanon: The instructional plan and materials are very suited to the topic and the learners are very eager to participate in the discussion.
	May 6, 2024	12:15 PM – 1:00 PM		 Ms. Marycon A. Bataanon	The pilot-testing was successfully implemented for the Kindergarten students after the two-week suspension of classes. The young learners have shown engagement and active participation in the activities for the learning session.	Ms. Bataanon: The instructional plan and materials are very suited and engaging to the learners.	Ms. Bataanon: All the instructional materials provided by Reine was interactive and very effective because the learners would be able to understand the topic discussed by the teacher and they enjoyed learning the topic.

APPENDIX D

Needs and Context Analysis Summary Notes:

Notes

Instructional designer: Reine Gerbie Labarrete

Assessment method/s: sit-in observation and discussion with the gatekeeper and Kindergarten teacher/adviser

Target Audience

Grade Level: Kindergarten

Section: Gold

Teacher: Ms. Carol S. Rondolo

Profile of Students

Number of Students: 15, 10 boys, 5 girls

Age: ranges between 5 to 6 years old

Socio-economic status: upper lower to lower middle classes

Curriculum: follows the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum by the Department of Education (DepEd)

Potential performance gaps: linguistic gap, the use of wrong prepositions and pronouns in sentences

- The students are motivated whenever the teacher makes them watch short videos.
- The students appreciate more colorful learning materials than black and white printed resources.
- In terms of learning preferences, the students can be deemed as visual, auditory and kinaesthetic learners.
- The students are bilingual and can speak in Tagalog and English, but English is more preferred and often used by the teacher and students when communicating.
- In terms of the current abilities of the students, they are able to follow directions and read and recognize basic words, but still have difficulty in writing long words and sentences.
- The use of prepositions are not included in the curriculum, as checked by my gatekeeper in the provided set of curriculum for Kindergarten.
- Since the learning activities and assessments are often textbook-based, students don't have opportunities for more interactive learning.
- There are no students that need special assistance/learning disability.

Learning Environment

Available resources used in the classroom:

- television to access YouTube videos
- blackboard
- worksheets: uncolorful, only often used in quarterly exams

Potential instructional needs: uses of media, visuals, colorful materials for motivation

APPENDIX E

Instructional Plan Utilized in Implementing the Piloted Activities:

Kindergarten

Language

Instructional Plan on Teaching
Prepositions

Designed by: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Instructional Plan for Session No. 1

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of in, on, under and over.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: In, On, Under, Over

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- a. identify the prepositions of in, on, under and over;
- b. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- c. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: box, toys, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Methodology

Preparation

Introductory Activity

- Share to the students that the new lesson that they will be learning for the Language subject is prepositions of place.
- Demonstrate the concepts of prepositions by showing the provided flashcards to the whole class with images of a star in different positions in relation to a box. *(Two sets of flashcards will be given, and the teacher may choose to pass on one set of flashcards to the students for a closer look.)*
- Let the students recognize the prepositions by asking them to repeat the words or going back and forth in flipping the flashcards.
- Downloadable link to the flashcards:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDPx_1_R4/lK4uitYR5FzDr7_Vv-a4sq/view?utm_content=DAGDPx_1_R4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Presentation

- Play the video entitled "Where is it?" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011) on prepositions: <https://youtu.be/8F0NYBBKczM?si=PmAcPQKHGQT2TWz->
- Play the video entitled "On In Under" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011): https://youtu.be/jSvjtePg_TE?si=r1MbnCrzvf59e5tx
- Play the video entitled "On In Under Song For Kids | Learn English Kids" by Dream English Kids (2014): <https://youtu.be/3VwQrnA6dkY?si=oph4HPbHIUlns75r>
- Present the multimedia presentation and display it on the mini television or laptop.
- Downloadable link to the multimedia presentation for Session No. 1: https://www.convo.com/design/DAGNz7LVbKQ/vD3sVkdMftO6n-ICjLTB_Q/vi ew?utm_content=DAGNz7LVbKQ&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor
- Present the following:
 - Show a picture of a bridge and encourage the students to observe it.
 - *A preposition is a bridge.*
 - *A preposition is a bridge that comes before a noun (or pronoun) and connects it to the rest of the sentence.*
 - Formula: rest of the sentence - preposition - noun (e.g. Max loves to rest on the mat.)
 - Explain the differences of "in" and "on," as well as "under" or "over" to students using the multimedia presentation.
 - *We use in when a person, thing or animal is inside another thing. We use on when a person, thing or animal is on top of another thing. We use under when a person, thing or animal is below another thing. We use over when a person, thing or animal is above another thing.*
 - After going through each preposition, examples using sentences with corresponding images are included to help the students understand the concept better.

Activity

- Engage the students by facilitating a hands-on activity wherein students must categorize an object as in, on, under or over.
- Using the provided box and toys, let the students place a toy in a position of either in, on, under or over in relation to the box.
- Provide a toy to each student and encourage them to place it in a position of either in, on, under or over in relation to the box and describe it by encouraging them to create their own sentence.

Application

Activity

- Have the students bring an object out of their bags and ask them to place it accordingly in, on, under or over their chair and ask them to create their own sentence.
- Compliment the students on their ability to correctly categorize the toys. This can be done through a reward system, such as by providing them treats, every time they use the correct preposition in a sentence with the corresponding position of the object in relation to their chair.

Presentation

- Present the multimedia presentation that displays sentences with corresponding images wherein students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions.
Examples:
The vegetables are in the basket.
The apple is on the book.
The cat is under the chair.
The dog is jumping over the fence.
- Engage the students in practicing the use of prepositions by encouraging each student to fill-in-the-blanks of the sentences with the correct prepositions and asking them to read the complete sentences.
- Provide treats every time a student successfully completes a sentence with the correct preposition.

Assessment

- Distribute the printed worksheets and have the students complete the activity individually where they must match the correct preposition of the sentence as shown on each image.
- Roam around the classroom to provide assistance and feedback as needed.
- After the students completed the worksheets, review the answers to each number together as a class.
- Downloadable link to Session No. 1 Worksheets:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN8VB3jhM/myQ6LPKccMc_6JO3_ci9-w/viaw?utm_content=DAGN8VB3jhM&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Concluding

- Review the students on what they have learned and check their understanding. This is to reinforce their understanding of the lesson on prepositions.
- Announce that for the next learning session, they will be learning another set of prepositions which are behind, in front of, beside and between.

Instructional Plan for Session No. 2

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: Behind, In Front Of, Beside, Between

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- a. identify the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between;
- b. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- c. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: two boxes, printed objects, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Methodology

Preparation

Introductory Activity

- Share to the students that the lesson that they will be learning for the Language subject is prepositions of place.
- Demonstrate the concepts of prepositions by showing the provided flashcards to the whole class with images of a star in different positions in relation to the box/es. *(Two sets of flashcards will be given, and the teacher may choose to pass on one set of flashcards to the students for a closer look.)*
- Review the students on the prepositions they learned in the first learning session through the use of flashcards.

- Let the students recognize the prepositions by asking them to repeat the words or going back and forth in flipping the flashcards.
- Downloadable link to the flashcards:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDPx_1_R4/lK4uitYR5FzDr7_Vv-a4sq/view?utm_content=DAGDPx_1_R4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Presentation

- Play the video entitled "In Front Of, Behind, Between" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011) on prepositions:
https://youtu.be/xERTESWbqhU?si=6wBvZxq-YR_2kcEi
- Play the video entitled "Prepositions of place for children - The concept of space, for kids - Where things are" by the Smile and Learn - English (2019):
<https://youtu.be/niPyVnC6W5g?si=NxUEj1HwixXclUGt>
- Play the video entitled "English Prepositions - In front of, behind, between | Lingokids" by Lingokids Songs and Playlearning (2017):
https://youtu.be/YvmlfB6xZ2l?si=C7pwfmsDqh_xKQzU
- Share to the students that the videos they watched explain the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.
- Present the multimedia presentation and display it on the mini television or laptop.
- Downloadable link to the multimedia presentation for Session No. 2:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN2HhSN_4/74RadMeGqMt0tsqlbGY0agq/view?utm_content=DAGN2HhSN_4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor
- Present the following:
 - Refresh the students on the concept of preposition.
 - *A preposition is a bridge.*
 - *A preposition is a bridge that comes before a noun (or pronoun) and connects it to the rest of the sentence.*
 - Formula: rest of the sentence - preposition - noun (e.g. Max loves to peek behind the fence.)
 - Explain the differences of "behind," "in front of," "beside" and "between" to students using the multimedia presentation.

- We use behind when a person, thing or animal is at the back of another person, thing or animal. We use in front of when a person, thing or animal is before another person, thing or animal. We use beside when a person, thing or animal is next to another person, thing or animal. We use between when a person, thing or animal is in the middle of two persons, things or animals.
- After going through each preposition, examples using sentences with corresponding images are included to help the students understand the concept better.

Application

Activity

- Engage the students by facilitating a hands-on activity wherein students must follow an order and categorize an object as behind, in front of, beside or between.
- Ask the students to raise their hands and have each of the volunteers go to the front of the class and order them to pick a paper with a printed object.
- Using the provided boxes and printed objects, instruct the students to place the printed object accordingly in a position of either behind, in front of, beside or between the boxes or other things.

Examples:

Please put the bag behind the box.

Please put the microphone in front of the desk.

Please put the umbrella beside your bag.

Please put the ball between the boxes.

- Downloadable link to the printed objects:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN8bqXZak/gzzvlyOS0cG0wWBZHFnbwQ/view?utm_content=DAGN8bqXZak&utm_campaign=designshore&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Presentation

- Present the multimedia presentation that displays sentences with corresponding images wherein students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions.
Examples:
The giraffe is behind the tree.
The students are in front of the school.
The doctor is standing beside the patient.
The cat is sitting between the boxes.
- Engage the students in practicing the use of prepositions by encouraging each student to fill-in-the-blanks of the sentences with the correct prepositions and asking them to read the complete sentences.
- Provide treats every time a student successfully completes a sentence with the correct preposition.

Assessment

- Distribute the printed worksheets and have the students complete the activity individually where they must match the correct preposition of the sentence and phrase as shown on each image.
- Roam around the classroom to provide assistance and feedback as needed.
- After the students completed the worksheets, review the answers to each number together as a class.
- Downloadable link to Session No. 2 Worksheets:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDWmOmyeU/o-ZpoubXMI3ESqMGhOzN0g/view?utm_content=DAGDWmOmyeU&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Concluding

- Review the students on what they have learned and check their understanding. This is to reinforce their understanding of the lesson on prepositions.

APPENDIX F

Instructional Materials Utilized in the Learning Sessions

a) Multimedia Presentations:

Learning Session No. 1 -

https://www.canva.com/design/DAGNz7LVbKQ/vD3sVkdMftO6n-ICjLTB_Q/view?utm_content=DAGNz7LVbKQ&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Learning Session No. 2 -

https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN2HhSN_4/74RadMeGqMt0tsqIbGY0gg/view?utm_content=DAGN2HhSN_4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

b) Worksheets:

Learning Session No. 1 -

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/17V0Kj7R8nn3mpFcJEKhGcBYjjld-47f-/view?usp=sharing>

Learning Session No. 2 -

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pB-OSrZjFdKGyJszAGUSLEJUPliiUAHu/view?usp=sharing>

c) Printed Flashcards:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pOkII4IFwu0uit7wweH7IEckEO8AQwOP/view?usp=sharing>

d) Printed Objects:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T3r4lOq82wyvG_rhhkBNCHpFtbryWESk/view?usp=s

[haring](#)

APPENDIX G

Sequence of Photo Evidences of Pilot-Testing for Learning Session No. 1:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1tj2nBA83PLBGm5Nd43kRlq-eISKKFhHB/view?usp=sharing>

APPENDIX H

Sequence of Photo Evidences of Pilot-Testing for Learning Session No. 2:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/16G-BkOjXg0wEAfyt6SRpQhbZid5jlCQK/view?usp=sharing>

EDS 199 - Special
Project
Instructional
Design
Rubric

The lesson demo will be evaluated using this rubric. You may use this to guide you in developing and implementing your lessons.

Criteria	Strongly Agree (5 pts)	Agree (4.5 pts)	Neutral (4 pts)	Disagree (3.5 pts)	Strongly Disagree (3 pts)
Learning Unit					
a. Instructional Objectives					
The learning objectives are specific (states specifically the behavior to be observed).	✓				
The learning objectives are observable (uses action words that can be clearly observed).	✓				
The learning objectives are measurable.	✓				
The learning objectives are achievable given the context and the available time and resources.	✓				
The components of the learning objectives are complete (behavior, condition, and performance).	✓				
The learning objectives are meaningful.	✓				
b. Opening					
The opening includes a guide or an activity that would clearly convey to the students:	✓				
- what they are going to learn in the session/ lesson	✓				
- the significance and relevance of the instruction/ lesson/ course	✓				
- how the lesson/instruction relates to what has been done/learned previously.	✓				
- communicates to students how the learning will occur.	✓				
The opening provides a motivational activity that stimulates students' interest and desire to learn more about the lesson.	✓				
- The opening engages the students and makes clear any behavioral expectations unique to the particular plan	✓				
- The opening assesses students' understanding of the lesson's purpose and procedure by allowing them time to ask clarifying questions about the purpose of the lesson or the final product, and/or by asking them to summarize what it is that you want them to take away from the lesson opening.	✓				
- It is specified how expectations of behavior will be communicated and modeled to the students.	✓				
c. Instruction Proper					
The instruction:					
- clarifies how the activities align to the learning objectives.	✓				
- is sequenced coherently and logically to maximize learning.	✓				
- provides opportunities for active exploration and application of process skills.	✓				
- provides hands-on experience.	✓				
- provides scaffolds for practice exercises and learning	✓				
- provides opportunities for students to discover and construct knowledge, and be actively engage in their learning.	✓				
- provides opportunities to express their own explanations and ideas first before the teacher provides an explanation.	✓				
- uses multiple approaches for discovering, presenting, and processing new information.	✓				
- provides students assistance in exploring the concepts, phenomena, ideas of the Lesson	✓				
- helps the students discuss and reflect on their findings, data, and analyses, and see what others found, to compare their ideas to other students' and experts on the topic.	✓				
- emphasizes and reiterates key points without glossing over ideas or drowning students in detail.	✓				
- targets potential misunderstandings and checks for understanding.	✓				
- has provisions for monitoring and correcting student performance.	✓				

APPENDIX J

Scanned Evaluation Tool and Overall Comment:

CHECKLIST FOR EVALUATING LEARNING MATERIALS

1.

Materials:	1	2	3	4	5
Quality of content					
Is the material appropriate for young learners?					✓
Are the learning objectives clear?					✓
Is the content current, relevant, and accurate?					✓
Is the content appropriate to the needs of the targeted group?					✓

2.

Materials:	1	2	3	4	5
Potential effectiveness as a teaching-learning tool					
Does the material present opportunities for task-based learning?					✓
Does the material present options for meeting individual needs?					✓
Does the material satisfy the various teaching and learning styles?					✓
Can the material be adapted to meet the needs of the targeted group?					✓

3.

Materials:	1	2	3	4	5
Ease of use (for practitioners and learners)					
Does the material present information in appealing ways?					✓
Does the material provide flexibility in its use?					✓
Does the material support self-directed learning?					✓

1 - Strongly disagree

4 - Agree

2 - Disagree

5 - Strongly agree

3 - Neither agree or disagree

Note: Tick (/) if the material is in accordance with the description and tick (X) for the opposite.

MARYCON A. BATAAYON

The materials needed is very compatible and captured the attention of the learners. They participated actively and lively to the presentation and the materials is very engaging.

(Adapted from:

<https://www.scribd.com/doc/179290138/Checklist-for-evaluating-learning-materials-d>

[ocx](#))

APPENDIX K

Modified Instructional Plan:

Kindergarten

Language

Instructional Plan on Teaching
Prepositions

Designed by: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Instructional Plan for Session No. 1

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of in, on, under and over.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: In, On, Under, Over

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- a. identify the prepositions of in, on, under and over;
- b. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- c. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: box, toys, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Methodology

Preparation

Introductory Activity

- Share to the students that the new lesson that they will be learning for the Language subject is prepositions of place.
- Demonstrate the concepts of prepositions by showing the provided flashcards to the whole class with images of a star in different positions in relation to a box. *(Two sets of flashcards will be given, and the teacher may choose to pass on one set of flashcards to the students for a closer look.)*
- Let the students recognize the prepositions by asking them to repeat the words or going back and forth in flipping the flashcards.
- Downloadable link to the flashcards:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDPx_1_R4/lK4uitYR5FzDr7_Vv-a4sq/view?utm_content=DAGDPx_1_R4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Presentation

- Play the video entitled "Where is it?" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011) on prepositions: <https://youtu.be/8F0NYBBKczM?si=PmAcPQKHGQT2TWz->
- Play the video entitled "On In Under" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011): https://youtu.be/jSvjtePq_TE?si=r1MbnCrzvf59e5tx
- Play the video entitled "On In Under Song For Kids | Learn English Kids" by Dream English Kids (2014): <https://youtu.be/3VwQrnA6dkY?si=oph4HPbHIUlns75r>
- Present the multimedia presentation and display it on the mini television, laptop or projector.
- Downloadable link to the multimedia presentation for Session No. 1: https://www.convo.com/design/DAGNz7LVbKQ/vD3sVkdMftO6n-ICjLTB_Q/viaw?utm_content=DAGNz7LVbKQ&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor
- Present the following:
 - Show a picture of a bridge and encourage the students to observe it.
 - *A preposition is a bridge.*
 - *A preposition is a bridge that comes before a noun (or pronoun) and connects it to the rest of the sentence.*
 - Formula: rest of the sentence - preposition - noun (e.g. Max loves to rest on the mat.)
 - Explain the differences of "in" and "on," as well as "under" or "over" to students using the multimedia presentation.
 - *We use in when a person, thing or animal is inside another thing. We use on when a person, thing or animal is on top of another thing. We use under when a person, thing or animal is below another thing. We use over when a person, thing or animal is above another thing.*
 - After going through each preposition, examples using sentences with corresponding images are included to help the students understand the concept better.

Activity

- Engage the students by facilitating a hands-on activity wherein students must categorize an object as in, on, under or over.
- Using the provided box and toys, let the students place a toy in a position of either in, on, under or over in relation to the box.
- Provide a toy to each student and encourage them to place it in a position of either in, on, under or over in relation to the box and describe it by encouraging them to create their own sentence.

Application

Activity

- Have the students bring an object out of their bags and ask them to place it accordingly in, on, under or over their chair and ask them to create their own sentence.
- Compliment the students on their ability to correctly categorize the toys. This can be done through a reward system, such as by providing them treats, every time they use the correct preposition in a sentence with the corresponding position of the object in relation to their chair.

Instructional Plan for Session No. 2

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of in, on, under and over.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: In, On, Under, Over

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- d. identify the prepositions of in, on, under and over;
- e. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- f. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: box, toys, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Methodology

Recall

- Ask the students if they remember what they learned in the first learning session about the prepositions of in, on, under and over.
- Explain to the students that they will be learning the same set of prepositions through a fill-in-the-blanks activity and worksheets. This activity will help reinforce their understanding of prepositions and how to use them in sentences. Additionally, the multimedia presentation will provide visual aids to support their learning.

Application

Presentation

- Present the multimedia presentation that displays sentences with corresponding images wherein students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions.

Examples:

The vegetables are in the basket.

The apple is on the book.

The cat is under the chair.

The dog is jumping over the fence.

- Engage the students in practicing the use of prepositions by encouraging each student to fill-in-the-blanks of the sentences with the correct prepositions and asking them to read the complete sentences.
- Provide treats every time a student successfully completes a sentence with the correct preposition.

Assessment

- Distribute the printed worksheets and have the students complete the activity individually where they must match the correct preposition of the sentence as shown on each image.
- Room around the classroom to provide assistance and feedback as needed.
- After the students completed the worksheets, review the answers to each number together as a class.
- Downloadable link to Session No. 1 Worksheets:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN8VB3jhM/myQ6LPKccMc_6JO3_ci9-w/vieu?utm_content=DAGN8VB3jhM&utm_campaign=designshore&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Concluding

- Review the students on what they have learned and check their understanding. This is to reinforce their understanding of the lesson on prepositions.
- Announce that for the next learning session, they will be learning another set of prepositions which are behind, in front of, beside and between.

Instructional Plan for Session No. 3

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: Behind, In Front Of, Beside, Between

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- a. identify the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between;
- b. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- c. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: two boxes, printed objects, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Methodology

Preparation

Introductory Activity

- Share to the students that the lesson that they will be learning for the Language subject is prepositions of place.
- Demonstrate the concepts of prepositions by showing the provided flashcards to the whole class with images of a star in different positions in relation to the box/es. *(Two sets of flashcards will be given, and the teacher may choose to pass on one set of flashcards to the students for a closer look.)*
- Review the students on the prepositions they learned in the first learning session through the use of flashcards.

- Let the students recognize the prepositions by asking them to repeat the words or going back and forth in flipping the flashcards.
- Downloadable link to the flashcards:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDPx_1_R4/lK4uitYR5FzDr7_Vv-a4sq/view?utm_content=DAGDPx_1_R4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Presentation

- Play the video entitled "In Front Of, Behind, Between" by Maple Leaf Learning (2011) on prepositions:
https://youtu.be/xERTESWbqhU?si=6wBvZxq-YR_2kcEi
- Play the video entitled "Prepositions of place for children - The concept of space, for kids - Where things are" by the Smile and Learn - English (2019):
<https://youtu.be/niPyVnC6W5g?si=NxUEj1HwixXclUGt>
- Play the video entitled "English Prepositions - In front of, behind, between | Lingokids" by Lingokids Songs and Playlearning (2017):
https://youtu.be/YvmlfB6xZ2l?si=C7pwfmsDqh_xKQzU
- Share to the students that the videos they watched explain the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.
- Present the multimedia presentation and display it on the mini television, laptop or projector.
- Downloadable link to the multimedia presentation for Session No. 2:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN2HhSN_4/74RadMeGqMt0tsqlbGY0ag/view?utm_content=DAGN2HhSN_4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor
- Present the following:
 - Refresh the students on the concept of preposition.
 - *A preposition is a bridge.*
 - *A preposition is a bridge that comes before a noun (or pronoun) and connects it to the rest of the sentence.*
 - Formula: rest of the sentence - preposition - noun (e.g. Max loves to peek behind the fence.)
 - Explain the differences of "behind," "in front of," "beside" and "between" to students using the multimedia presentation.

- We use behind when a person, thing or animal is at the back of another person, thing or animal. We use in front of when a person, thing or animal is before another person, thing or animal. We use beside when a person, thing or animal is next to another person, thing or animal. We use between when a person, thing or animal is in the middle of two persons, things or animals.
- After going through each preposition, examples using sentences with corresponding images are included to help the students understand the concept better.

Application

Activity

- Engage the students by facilitating a hands-on activity wherein students must follow an order and categorize an object as behind, in front of, beside or between.
- Ask the students to raise their hands and have each of the volunteers go to the front of the class and order them to pick a paper with a printed object.
- Using the provided boxes and printed objects, instruct the students to place the printed object accordingly in a position of either behind, in front of, beside or between the boxes or other things.

Examples:

Please put the bag behind the box.

Please put the microphone in front of the desk.

Please put the umbrella beside your bag.

Please put the ball between the boxes.

- Downloadable link to the printed objects:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGN8bqXZak/gzzvlyOS0cG0wWBZHFnbwQ/view?utm_content=DAGN8bqXZak&utm_campaign=designshore&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Instructional Plan for Session No. 4

Name of Teacher:

Name of Instructional Designer: Reine Gerbie R. Labarrete

Grade level: Kindergarten

Quarter: 4th

Learning Area: Language

Competencies: Identifying, recognizing and applying prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.

Duration: 45 minutes

Key understandings to be developed: Prepositions of Place: Behind, In Front Of, Beside, Between

Learning Objectives:

Students will be able to:

- d. identify the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between;
- e. recognize the prepositions of place; and
- f. apply the use of prepositions in sentences.

Resources Needed: two boxes, printed objects, multimedia presentation, worksheets

Recall

- Ask the students if they remember what they learned in the third learning session about the prepositions of behind, in front of, beside and between.
- Explain to the students that they will be learning the same set of prepositions through a fill-in-the-blanks activity and worksheets. This is to reinforce the correct use of prepositions in sentences to enhance communication skills.

Methodology

Application

Presentation

- Present the multimedia presentation that displays sentences with corresponding images wherein students must fill-in-the-blanks with the correct prepositions.
Examples:
The giraffe is behind the tree.
The students are in front of the school.
The doctor is standing beside the patient.
The cat is sitting between the boxes.
- Engage the students in practicing the use of prepositions by encouraging each student to fill-in-the-blanks of the sentences with the correct prepositions and asking them to read the complete sentences.
- Provide treats every time a student successfully completes a sentence with the correct preposition.

Assessment

- Distribute the printed worksheets and have the students complete the activity individually where they must match the correct preposition of the sentence and phrase as shown on each image.
- Roam around the classroom to provide assistance and feedback as needed.
- After the students completed the worksheets, review the answers to each number together as a class.
- Downloadable link to Session No. 2 Worksheets:
https://www.canva.com/design/DAGDWmOmyeU/o-ZpoubXMI3ESqMGhOzN0g/view?utm_content=DAGDWmOmyeU&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=editor

Concluding

- Review the students on what they have learned and check their understanding. This is to reinforce their understanding of the lesson on prepositions.